

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction Between Persulphate and Silver Ion

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A detailed study of this reaction was found to be very similar to the silver catalysed persulphate oxidation of Mn (II), Tl(I), V^{5+} and Ce (III). The rate was found to be of the order of 0.3-0.61/mol/min as found in the case of Mn (II) or Tl (I). The rate determining step in all these reactions is the same. The rate expression is given by

$$\frac{-\text{(S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-})}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 \text{(S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) \text{(Ag}^+)}{k_a + k_3 \text{(Ag}^+)}$$

or $\frac{k_1 k_2}{k_a} \text{(S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) \text{(Ag}^+)$ if $k_a \gg k_3 \text{(Ag}^+)$. Energy and entropy of activation have nearly equal values in all these oxidations.

In a recent paper¹, we briefly reported this reaction in connection with the oxidation of Tl(I). Encouraged by the fact that the reaction has a rate constant of the same order of magnitude as that of Tl(I), a detailed study of the kinetics seemed necessary to know more about the mechanism because the present reaction has a distinct advantage over other silver catalysed oxidations in not being complicated by the presence of the substrate. In the present case, Ag(II) formed from the reactants oxidised water to oxygen because there is nothing else to be oxidised. The mechanism as will be seen later, involves mainly two steps. One, in which higher valent silver is produced, is slow. The other in which water is oxidised, is faster. The kinetics have been followed by estimating the persulphate iodometrically. In this method higher valent silver will also liberate iodine, but because it is used up almost instantaneously, its concentration never becomes significant. Colorimetric measurements at $475 \mu\mu$ soon give a constant absorption indicating a stationary concentration for Ag(II), but insignificant in comparison to that of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$; Ag(II) or Ag(III), therefore, does not interfere with the analytical method.

A number of stable complexes of higher valent silver are reported²⁻⁷ and therefore, an attempt was made to follow the kinetics by analysing the complexes formed. Addition of pyridine gives orange, and 1-10 phenanthroline or α - α' -bipyridyl gives brown or red silky precipitate. The precipitate is separated by centrifuging it and then estimated iodometrically. The estimation could be made with difficulty because the precipitate does not dissolve

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readily in water or dilute acids and does not liberate iodine instantaneously. It is found that a stationary concentration of the complex is soon reached and this concentration of the complex depends upon the Ag(I) initially taken and may be comparable to the concentration of persulphate. It was also found that the decrease in persulphate concentration becomes much slower in presence of complexing agents because the concentration of Ag(I) goes in the complex in the form of Ag(II). The complex precipitates of 1,10-phenanthroline as said earlier, is not readily soluble and hence the reduction of Ag(II) to Ag(I) does not take place readily. Pyridine complex is readily soluble in acid solution and, therefore, is readily reduced to Ag(I). All the results are briefly shown in Table I.

TABLE I

$(S_2O_8^{2-}) = 0.01M$; $(Ag^+) = 0.005M$; $(H_2SO_4) = 0.72N$
Total Reaction Mixture = 100 ml; 5 ml aliquots analysed.

Time Mins.	Phenanthroline complex 5ml of 0.5% solution		Pyridine complex 0.5 ml.		
	Iodometric Value of R. M. in ml of 0.02N $S_2O_8^{2-}$	Iodometric Value of the precipitate in ml of 0.02N $S_2O_8^{2-}$	Optical Density at at 475 $m\mu$	Iodometric Value of R. M. in ml of 0.02N $S_2O_8^{2-}$	Optical Density at 475 $m\mu$
0	4.9	—	—	4.90	—
15	4.20	1.80	0.15	2.50	0.35
30	4.15	1.85	0.15	1.95	0.35
45	4.05	1.85	0.15	—	—
60	3.90	1.85	0.15	1.25	0.35

All these preliminary investigations revealed that the kinetics of the reaction cannot be followed by Ag(II) complexation. Even if this would have been possible the presence of complexing reagents would have largely affected the kinetics.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were either B.D.H. AnalaR or E. Merck G.R. quality. Water used was doubly distilled in pyrex glass vessels. Potassium persulphate was freshly prepared by direct weighing and its concentration checked frequently by Eckardt's⁸ method. Sodium perchlorate was prepared from perchloric acid by titration against a solution of Na_2CO_3 to pH 7.

Calculated quantities of perchloric acid, silver nitrate and water were taken in the reaction vessel placed in a thermostat at 35°. Persulphate solution was separately thermostated. Calculated quantity of persulphate was then added to the reaction vessel. The total volume of the reaction mixture was 100 ml. After suitable intervals, 5 ml aliquot of the reaction mixture was pipetted out and determined for persulphate⁹. The reaction is influenced by ionic strength and hence in order to compare the results amongst themselves, the ionic strength was kept almost constant at some high value by the addition of $NaClO_4$. Optical density measurements were made with the Bausch & Lomb Colorimeter arbitrarily at 475 $m\mu$.

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Double-distilled water¹⁰⁻¹¹ was used in all the experiments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rate was found to be of first order with respect to persulphate. The rate of reaction depends on Ag(I) concentration also. The observed rate constant divided by the first power of Ag(I) concentration gives a constant number indicating that the Ag(I) concentration during run remains constant and the rate is first order with respect to Ag(I) also. These constants have been referred to as catalytic constants, k_r . The observed rate constant was obtained by the slope of the linear plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time. k_r was calculated by the expression.

$$k_r = \frac{2.303 \times \text{slope}}{(\text{Ag}^+)}$$

A few representative time order plot for different concentrations of the reactants are shown in figure 1.

FIG 1.

The constants at various concentrations of persulphate and Ag(I) are given in Table II and III respectively. The temperature is 35° unless otherwise mentioned.

TABLE II

First order dependence on persulphate

$(\text{Ag}^+) = 0.005\text{M}$; $(\text{HClO}_4) = 0.182\text{M}$; $(\text{NaClO}_4) = 0.50\text{M}$

$(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-})$, M 0.002, 0.004, 0.006, 0.008, 0.01, 0.015, 0.020, 0.025, 0.040.

k_r (1/mol/min) 0.631, 0.614, 0.614, 0.614, 0.590, 0.60, 0.576, 0.561, 0.530.

TABLE III

Effect of Ag⁺ conc.

$(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) = 0.01\text{M}$; $(\text{HClO}_4) = 0.182\text{M}$; $(\text{NaClO}_4) = 0.50\text{M}$

(Ag^+) , M	0.002	0.005	0.0075	0.01	0.02
$k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	1.20	2.95	4.35	5.90	11.81
k_r (1/mol/min)	0.60	0.59	0.58	0.59	0.59

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The rate constants slightly decrease with increasing concentration of persulphate probably because the steady state concentration of Ag(II) becomes significant at higher concentration of persulphate. This Ag(II) also liberates iodine when analysing for persulphate, thus giving higher values for persulphate and consequently lower values of rate constants.

The rate does not depend on the hydrogen ion concentration. The slight decrease (Table IV) may be explained on the basis of increase in ionic strength.

TABLE IV
($S_2O_8^{--}$) = 0.01M; (Ag^+) = 0.005M; ($NaClO_4$) = 0.50M

($HClO_4$), M	0.045	0.091	0.182	0.364	0.546	0.728
k_r (1/mol/min)	0.598	0.590	0.590	0.561	0.550	0.548

The reaction is influenced by the change in ionic strength. The rate experiments were carried out at low concentrations of reactants to keep the ionic strength as low as possible¹². The concentration of perchloric acid, however, could not be reduced much to obviate the possibility of precipitation of black Ag(II) oxide¹³. The reactions being slow, were studied at 45°. A plot of $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ shows a straight line with a slope of -0.96 (fig. 2).

FIG. 2

Energy and Entropy of activation.

The reaction was studied at four different temperatures and the concentration of the reactants were also varied. The nature of reaction does not change. Table V shows these results at 30°, 40° and 45°.

TABLE V
Rate constants at different temperatures
($HClO_4$) = 0.182M; ($NaClO_4$) = 0.50M

30°		40°		45°	
(Ag^+) = 0.005M	($S_2O_8^{--}$) = 0.01M	(Ag^+) = 0.005M	($S_2O_8^{--}$) = 0.01M	(Ag^+) = 0.005M	($S_2O_8^{--}$) = 0.005M
1. 0.404 (0.005) ₁	0.404 (0.01) ₂	0.853 (0.005) ₁	0.837 (0.01) ₂	1.28 (0.005) ₁	1.25 (0.01) ₂
2. 0.404 (0.01) ₁	0.394 (0.015) ₂	0.845 (0.01) ₁	0.830 (0.015) ₂	1.28 (0.01) ₁	1.23 (0.015) ₂
3. 0.394 (0.015) ₁	0.404 (0.02) ₂	0.837 (0.015) ₁	0.821 (0.02) ₂	1.26 (0.015) ₁	1.21 (0.02) ₂
4. 0.384 (0.02) ₁	0.390 (0.025) ₂	0.830 (0.02) ₁	0.837 (0.025) ₂	1.23 (0.02) ₁	1.23 (0.025) ₂

Figures in parenthesis with subscript, 1 and 2 give molar concentrations of persulphate and Ag (I) respectively for which the rate constants in each column have been given.

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A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ gives a straight line from the slope of which, the energy of activation was found to be 14,200 calories.

DISCUSSION

The present reaction is similar almost in all respects to that of the oxidation of Tl(I) or that¹⁴ of Mn(II) as will be clear from Table VI.

TABLE VI
The silver catalysed persulphate oxidations at 35°

Oxidation of	μ Ionic Strength	k_p Catalytic constant 1/mol/min	E_a Energy of Acti- vation calories	ΔS Entropy of Activation c.s.u.
Mn (II)	0.637	0.540	15,020	-20.2
Tl (I)	0.772	0.547	13,220	-18.3
H ₂ O	0.740	0.575	14,200	-18.4

The rate determining step of the reaction, therefore, must be identical in all the three cases. The following mechanism, on the basis of the reasons advanced in an earlier paper¹ and on the basis of results of the present investigation may be proposed for the reaction between persulphate of Ag(I)

Reaction (3) may consist of a number of following steps as already given by Kirwin *et al.*², but all of them are fast as compared to k_1 , k_2 or k_3 and, therefore, they have all been included in k_4 .

Kirwin *et al.*² observed a rate constant of approximately 6 to $24 M^{-1}$ for the decomposition of Ag(III) whereas the observed rate constant in the present investigation is approximately $0.003 M^{-1}$. In the proposed mechanism Ag(III) is first formed, and this immediately gives Ag(II) through a rapid equilibrium(4). Noyes *et al.*¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have shown that there is very small concentration of Ag(III) in such an equilibrium. This rapid equilibrium has been proved by Ag(I) and Ag(II) exchange study also by Gordon and Wahl¹⁸.

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Application of the steady state treatment for SO_4^- leads to the rate law

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})(\text{Ag}^+)}{k_2 + k_3 (\text{Ag}^+)}$$

Initial rate was calculated by the plane mirror method¹⁹ and a plot of its reciprocal vs the reciprocal of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ concentration gave a straight line (Fig. 3) with a slope equal to $\frac{k_2}{k_1 k_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})}$

FIG. 3

If $k_2 \gg k_3 (\text{Ag}^+)$ the rate expression can be simplified to $\frac{-d(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})(\text{Ag}^+)}{k_2}$

The experimental and graphical values of $\frac{k_1 k_2}{k_2}$ are 0.60 and 0.66 respectively, which are of the same order of magnitude and in confirmation with the proposed mechanism. We prefer this mechanism to the reported²⁰ one,

(a) a plot $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ gives a slope of -1 and not -2;
 (b) the entropy²¹ change is expected to be more than -12 e. u. for the above step whereas experimentally found value is low;

(c) A plot of $1 \left[\frac{-d(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{--})}{dt} \right] \text{ vs } \frac{1}{(\text{Ag}^+)}$ gives a straight line with an intercept and

hence the rate determining step must be preceded by an equilibrium.

Effect of reaction products :

Sulphate and bisulphate had no effect on the rate, though their concentrations were varied twenty fold from 0.01M to 0.20M. This shows that the rate determining step(2) or any step prior to this is not a sulphate or bisulphate involving equilibrium step.

Effect of allyl acetate:

Allyl acetate is known to inhibit the persulphate oxidation^{22,23}, but in the present

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case a peculiar behaviour is noted. At low concentrations, the rate is faster and it becomes slower for higher concentrations.

TABLE VII

($S_2O_8^{2-}$) = 0.001M; (Ag^+) = 0.005M; ($HClO_4$) = 0.182M; ($NaClO_4$) = 0.50M							
(Allyl acetate) M	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50
k_r (1/mol/min.)	1.935	1.228	0.903	0.614	0.439	0.384	0.349

Allyl acetate is an effective scavenger²⁴ for SO_4^- radical ions and therefore, it may terminate the chain in a chain mechanism as in the oxidation of oxalate²⁵ or phosphorous acid²⁶. The present oxidation does not seem to involve chains and hence the action of allyl acetate can be explained only by postulating a different mechanism in the presence of allyl acetate. In case of Tl(I) oxidation also, the rate of decrease of persulphate concentration increased in presence of allyl acetate, but Tl(I) was not oxidised. It is very likely that allyl acetate might be undergoing both the processes; polymerisation by $SO_4^=$ because products with sulphate end groups²⁷ have been reported, and oxidation by $Ag(II)$. A few qualitative experiments have shown that the $Ag(II)$ complexes of pyridine or 1, 10 phenanthroline quickly react with allyl acetate giving colourless solution. It is difficult to say that allyl acetate inhibits these reactions or other reactions which are not chain mechanisms.

Previous studies have shown that there is no exchange^{26,27} between persulphate and S^{35} labelled sulphate under varied conditions, and, therefore, the following equilibrium may be slow: $S_2O_8^{2-} \rightleftharpoons 2 SO_4^-$, but this can be fast as well, if it is followed by the slow step

In the latter case it is not SO_4^- but $SO_4^=$ which is in equilibrium with the persulphate and the exchange reaction will be governed by step (7) which has been reported to be slow by a number of workers²⁸⁻³¹.

The work is still in progress particularly with respect to the effect of certain ions on persulphate oxidations. It is expected this study will lead to a more detailed picture of the mechanism.

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Received, October 12, 1966.

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